
Youth Digital Campaigns on Instagram for Educational Equity in Indonesia: A Case Study of @Sekolah.Tanahair

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ABSTRACT: With a focus on the @sekolah.tanahair account run by the Distrik Berisik community, this study investigates how Instagram works as a digital campaign tool to combat educational inequity in remote areas of Indonesia. This study examines digital interactions, content strategies, and participatory communication patterns using a qualitative case study approach and netnography. The results show that Instagram functions as a participatory platform that turns awareness into action, going beyond simply disseminating information. The campaign effectively garners public attention, cultivates empathy, and promotes active engagement through donations, volunteer work, and content sharing through the use of visual storytelling and emotionally compelling narratives. The campaign's three main phases awareness, engagement, and action showcase a methodical and successful communication approach.

Significantly, this study demonstrates how youth led digital projects may transform passive audiences into active contributors, producing real effects on educational development as well as social awareness. Instagram thus becomes a potent tool for social change and participatory communication.

KEYWORDS: Digital Campaign, Instagram, Educational Inequality, Participation, Youth

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of digital communication technology has significantly transformed how individuals access, produce, and disseminate information. Social media has emerged as a primary medium in this transformation, enabling communication that is fast, interactive, and participatory. Among various platforms, Instagram has evolved from a simple photo- and video-sharing application into a public communication space that facilitates information exchange, self-expression, and the articulation of public aspirations (Instagram, 2024). In this context, social media not only functions as a communication tool but also as a space for constructing digital identities and social relationships (Nasrullah, 2017). As emphasized by Castells (2009), users in the digital era are no longer passive recipients of information but active producers, positioning social media as a strategic arena for shaping public opinion and discourse. These results imply that media literacy education programs are an important response to growing concerns about the effects of online disinformation. Efficient method to considerably reduce the spread of disinformation by decreasing a user's propensity to spread satisfied with their networks (Facciani matthew,2023).

The transformation of communication in the digital era has also been widely discussed in contemporary communication studies. The shift from conventional media to digital platforms has created new patterns of interaction characterized by participatory, interactive, and user-generated communication. Digital media enables the formation of new public spaces where individuals actively construct meaning and engage in social discourse (Rianto & Desmalinda, 2025). In this regard, visual-based platforms such as Instagram play a crucial role in shaping audience engagement. The use of images, videos, and narratives has been shown to strengthen emotional connections and improve the effectiveness of communication messages in digital campaigns (Nuryati et al., 2025). Furthermore, the increasingly selective and participatory behavior of digital audiences requires adaptive and audience-oriented communication strategies to maintain engagement and relevance (Balqis & Rahayu, 2025).

The growing role of social media has significantly influenced how social issues are communicated, including in the fields of education and development. Previous studies indicate that social media enhances public engagement and participation by facilitating the formation of networks that support message dissemination (Boyd & Ellison, 2007) and encouraging interaction around social issues (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Digital campaigns, in particular, have been proven effective in increasing public awareness and mobilizing collective action (Naryoso, Febriyani, & Kaloka, 2022). Moreover, the development of social capital through digital networks contributes to strengthening community involvement in educational development (Mikiewicz & de Araújo, 2021).

In the Indonesian context, educational inequality remains a critical and persistent issue, particularly in remote and

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underdeveloped regions. Limitations in infrastructure, shortages of qualified teachers, and restricted access to educational resources continue to hinder equal learning opportunities (Central Statistics Agency of Indonesia, 2023; Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, 2023). These challenges are further compounded by geographical barriers, socio-cultural perceptions regarding the importance of education, and economic constraints. In addition, the implementation of the “Merdeka” Curriculum, which emphasizes digital literacy and innovative learning, has not been evenly realized due to limited internet access and inadequate facilities in rural areas.

Alongside educational challenges, Indonesia also faces structural issues in the agricultural sector, particularly related to declining youth participation. The agricultural workforce is increasingly dominated by older generations, while younger individuals tend to migrate to urban areas and pursue non-agricultural careers. This trend reflects global patterns identified by the Food and Agriculture Organization (2022), which highlights the aging agricultural workforce as a major concern for sustainability and food security. Without innovative strategies to engage young people, this condition may threaten the long-term resilience of the agricultural sector. In response to these challenges, digital media has emerged as a strategic tool for development communication and social campaigns. According to Rogers and Storey (1987), communication campaigns function not only as channels for information dissemination but also as efforts to influence attitudes and behaviors in achieving development goals. Globally, youth-led digital initiatives have demonstrated their potential in shaping public awareness and influencing policy. For example, the Teach the Future movement in the United Kingdom utilizes digital platforms to advocate for the integration of climate education into the curriculum (Teach the Future, 2023), while the GRIN Campaign in the United States employs viral media strategies to address social issues such as bullying and discrimination (GRIN Campaign, 2013). In the agricultural sector, young farmers in developing regions have also utilized platforms such as TikTok to disseminate knowledge, promote products, and build market networks (TikTok, 2024).

In Indonesia, this potential is reinforced by the rapid growth of social media usage. The Digital 2024 report shows that Indonesia has more than 191 million active social media users, the majority of whom are young people (We Are Social & Meltwater, 2024). This demographic dominance creates significant opportunities for youth to utilize digital platforms as instruments for raising awareness, mobilizing participation, and encouraging social change in various development sectors.

One example of youth-driven digital initiatives is the Distrik Berisik community through its Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair, which highlights the conditions of formal education in remote areas of Indonesia. The account utilizes visual storytelling in the form of photos, videos, and narratives to present the realities of educational inequality. This content functions not only as an information medium but also as a space for public aspiration, fostering empathy, social solidarity, and participatory engagement. High levels of interaction, such as likes, comments, and donation participation, indicate that such digital campaigns are capable of mobilizing public awareness and encouraging community involvement.

Despite the growing number of digital campaign initiatives, academic research focusing on social media campaigns for educational development particularly those conducted by community-based movements on platforms such as Instagram remains limited. Most existing studies tend to focus on political communication, health campaigns, or commercial marketing contexts. Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap by examining how digital campaigns are utilized as media for information dissemination and public aspiration in addressing educational inequality and promoting agricultural independence.

Based on this background, the main research problem of this study is how the Distrik Berisik community utilizes Instagram as a medium for information and public aspiration in highlighting educational issues in remote areas, and how this digital campaign contributes to shaping public awareness and participatory communication. Accordingly, this study aims to analyze the strategies employed in digital campaigns through the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair in disseminating information, fostering public engagement, and encouraging broader participation in supporting equitable education and agricultural development in Indonesia.

- RQ1. How does Instagram function as a digital campaign medium in raising awareness of educational inequality in remote areas?
- RQ2. What digital communication strategies are used in Instagram based campaigns to encourage audience engagement?
- RQ3. What forms of audience participation are generated through the digital campaign in supporting educational equity?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this study, the author intends to conduct a literature review as a step in developing a research proposal to update this research and avoid similarities with previous research or previous thesis titles. After conducting the literature review, the researcher found several titles discussing the use and strategies of digital campaigns using social media.

A. Previous Research

First, an analysis by Unsil Al Huda (2025) found that digital advertising campaigns on social media (Instagram, WhatsApp, Facebook) significantly expanded the reach and increased public awareness of Islamic educational institutions in rural areas. Research by Masruroh, Shafa, and Uswatun Hasanah (JUMPA) also revealed that educational marketing strategies on social media, particularly Instagram and Facebook, can increase public engagement and the image of educational institutions, although their focus was more on school marketing than social campaigns.

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Second, a study by Mahmud MY et al. (2024) used qualitative methods to illustrate that formal educational institutions, such as madrasahs, utilize various social media platforms (Instagram, YouTube, WhatsApp) for student recruitment and communication with parents, supporting the notion that social media is a strategic tool in strengthening educational presence. Effective use of social media increases public engagement and strengthens the school's image, enhancing the competitiveness of educational institutions.

Third, the relationship between digital literacy and educational campaigns is also evident in research by Nurjuman & Priana (2022), who found that adolescents have a technical understanding of social media but lack critical awareness of the social impacts of digital content. This suggests that social media use can foster important digital literacy skills, such as critically evaluating content a particularly relevant aspect when educational campaigns on Instagram involve audiences who must sort through information.

Based on an analysis of eight previous studies examining digital social media campaigns and their relationship to education, it can be said that most studies demonstrate how effective social media, especially Instagram, is as a tool for social development and educational campaigns. The majority of previous studies focused on educational factors in general, not focusing on social issues such as the issue of educational disparities in remote areas. They only focused on increasing knowledge or awareness, the role of influencers in driving the spread of messages, and the level of engagement (likes, comments, and shares). The results of this study indicate that an effective digital campaign strategy through social media can influence public opinion, behavior, and engagement on educational issues. Furthermore, there is no research that focuses on the role of youth in educational development in disadvantaged areas.

B. Theoretical Framework

This study employs framing theory as the primary theoretical foundation to analyze digital campaign strategies for formal education development through the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair. This theory is used to understand how the issue of educational inequality in remote areas is constructed and presented through digital content, thereby influencing audience perceptions. In this context, framing functions not only as a means of delivering information but also as a tool for shaping meaning and public understanding.

Referring to Robert N. Entman's (1993) framing model, there are four key elements in the framing process: define problems, diagnose causes, make moral judgement, and treatment recommendation. In this study, these elements are used to examine how the @sekolah.tanahair account defines educational inequality as a social problem, identifies its causes such as limited infrastructure, constructs moral judgments that evoke empathy and social concern, and offers solutions through calls for participation such as donations and volunteer involvement.

In addition, this study applies campaign communication theory, which explains that a campaign is a systematically designed communication process aimed at influencing audience attitudes and behavior. Digital campaigns utilize social media as a medium for rapid, wide-reaching, and interactive message dissemination, employing strategic content formats such as visuals, narratives, and interactive features to enhance audience engagement.

The relationship between framing theory and campaign communication theory in this study is complementary. Campaign communication focuses on the strategic delivery of messages, while framing focuses on how those messages are constructed to create meaning and influence audience perception. The integration of these two theories allows for a more comprehensive analysis of the effectiveness of digital campaigns in promoting educational development through Instagram.

III. RESEACH METHOD

This study employs a qualitative method with a case study approach, aiming to gain an in depth understanding of a phenomenon, program, or social activity within its real-life context and this study also applies a netnographic approach to analyze digital interactions on Instagram, particularly focusing on user engagement, content patterns, and participatory communication within the @sekolah.tanahair account.

The case study approach was chosen because it allows for a comprehensive exploration of the digital campaign strategies carried out by the Distrik Berisik social community through the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair, particularly in the context of formal education development in remote areas of Indonesia. This study was conducted from Agustus to October 2025, focusing on digital campaign activities disseminated through the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair. The research employed both online and offline settings, consisting of online observation of the Instagram account and offline field observations through interviews with several relevant informants.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. *Result Youth, Digital Media, and Social Transformation*

The findings of this study confirm that youth play a strategic role as agents of social change in the digital era. Unlike previous generations that relied on physical mobilization, contemporary youth utilize digital platforms, creative content, and networked communication as instruments for social transformation. This shift reflects the broader transformation of communication patterns in the digital age, where participation is no longer limited by space and time.

However, the digital environment also presents a paradox. While it offers wider access to information and participation, it simultaneously introduces challenges such as information overload, misinformation, and short-lived engagement. Therefore, the effectiveness of youth-led digital initiatives depends not only on technological literacy but also on the ability to transform digital interaction into sustainable social impact. In this context, youth function as intermediaries who bridge marginalized communities particularly in education and agriculture with broader public awareness and resources.

Instagram as a Participatory Communication Space

The results show that Instagram functions not merely as a platform for content sharing but as a participatory communication space. As a visually oriented medium, Instagram enables the construction of powerful narratives through images, videos, and storytelling, which are capable of evoking emotional responses and fostering empathy.

The case of the @sekolah.tanahair account illustrates how digital campaigns can transform educational issues into shared public concerns. Visual documentation of inadequate school facilities, combined with persuasive narratives, successfully attracts public attention and encourages participation in the form of donations, discussions, and direct involvement. This indicates that audiences are not passive recipients but active participants who contribute to the dissemination and amplification of campaign messages.

This finding aligns with the concept of participatory communication in new media environments, where users simultaneously act as consumers and producers of information. In this sense, Instagram becomes a digital ecosystem that facilitates solidarity, social awareness, and collective action.

From Awareness to Action: The Dynamics of Digital Campaigns

The analysis reveals that the effectiveness of the digital campaign follows a structured communication process consisting of three main stages: awareness, engagement, and action.

First, awareness is built through visually compelling and emotionally engaging content that highlights real-life conditions in marginalized communities. Second, engagement is fostered through interactive features such as comments, sharing, and participatory calls to action, which create a sense of involvement among audiences. Third, action is realized when audiences translate awareness into tangible contributions, including donations, volunteering, and advocacy.

These findings support the argument that the success of digital campaigns should not be measured solely by engagement metrics, but by their ability to generate real social impact. The transition from online interaction to offline action represents the core strength of youth-led digital campaigns.

Cross-Sector Implications: Education and Agricultural Development

Although the primary focus of the campaign is educational inequality, the findings also highlight broader implications for development, particularly in relation to agriculture. Both sectors face structural challenges, including unequal access, limited resources, and declining youth participation. Digital platforms offer opportunities to address these challenges through cross-sector innovation. In agriculture, for instance, social media can be utilized for knowledge sharing, product promotion, and community building. The integration of digital technology with agricultural practices has the potential to reposition the sector as more attractive to younger generations.

This indicates that digital campaigns are not limited to awareness-building but can also contribute to long-term development strategies by fostering innovation, collaboration, and knowledge exchange across sectors. This section presents the research findings and discussion organized thematically, namely: (1) Instagram as an information medium, (2) Instagram as a space for public aspiration and participation, (3) digital campaign strategies, and (4) the impact of the campaign on educational development. Each theme integrates empirical findings with theoretical foundations to strengthen the analysis.

Instagram @sekolah.tanahair

The Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair is one of the social media accounts belonging to the Noisy District community with 3,103 followers and tens of thousands of likes (instagram @sekolah.tanahair).

[Figure Caption: Profail instagram @sekolah.tanahair]

Fig. 1. Researcher

A social community that cares about the community, the Noisy District community helps those in need, such as during natural disasters, criticizing the government, and in the field of educational development. Quoted from kumaran.com, the Noisy District community was founded by a social activist and influencer named Rian Fahardian, who frequently discusses social and political issues on his personal social media. The Noisy District is a youth discussion community that addresses social issues within the community and the government. They use social media as a medium for information and aspirations. One of their social media platforms is the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair. They created this social media platform with the aim of acting as a "mouthpiece for the community," meaning they, as young people, help the community convey their aspirations through their social media accounts, such as on Instagram @sekolah.tanahair.

Compared to other social community initiatives that also address educational issues such as the Instagram account @1000guru, which has a larger number of followers the content of that account lacks a clear issue focus and primarily shares documentation of *traveling and teaching* activities as well as volunteers' experiences, rather than conducting digital campaigns that introduce and highlight the actual conditions of schools. In contrast, the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair specifically focuses on the issue of formal educational inequality in remote areas by sharing posts that highlight the conditions of formal schools through its Instagram platform.

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On this account, they share various conditions of educational development in several remote areas, through photos, videos, and written narratives that depict the inadequate state of education, in terms of building infrastructure and inadequate educational facilities. On average, the posted content garnered approximately 2,000 to 1,000,000 views. The goal is for the wider community to see the conditions there and participate through donations or volunteering in the areas they support. Not only the community but also a form of information and criticism of the government so that the government pays more attention to education in remote areas.

1.) Instagram as an information medium

Based on observations and interviews, the @sekolah.tanahair account regularly uses Instagram as its primary platform to share information about the quality of education in remote areas of Indonesia. Narratives depicting educational challenges, inadequate facilities, and motivational stories from educators and students accompany each post. These reports effectively capture viewers' attention with poignant and educational images, highlighting key elements and narratives.

According to McQuail (2011), the participatory and interactive features of new media enable the general public to become both producers and consumers of information. This is demonstrated by active user interaction in direct messages and comments, where members of the public provide further details about the conditions of other schools in need of assistance, in addition to providing emotional support.

As a form of citizen journalism, the information provided by the Sekolah Tanah Air community helps raise public awareness of educational issues. Social media creates a new public space that allows for the rapid and widespread dissemination of social messages (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). Therefore, Instagram is crucial as an alternative source of information for educational advancement. For example, the first content uploaded to the social media account @sekolah.tanahair on March 4, 15, 17, 25, and 28, 2025, featured a short video of a school located in a remote area of South Sulawesi, specifically the Punraga Inpress Elementary School in Pujananting Village, Barru Regency, South Sulawesi. Here are some images uploaded by @sekolah.tanahair:

[Figure Caption: Instagram upload @sekolah.tanahair and image caption]

Fig 2, 3,4,5 Researcher

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In the post, the administrator of a local school provides information about education in a remote area of South Sulawesi, featuring video footage, photos, and a voiceover. The post highlights inadequate facilities, such as the road access to the school, where students and teachers must walk kilometers along a damaged road and cross extensive rice paddy embankments to reach their school. Furthermore, learning facilities, such as chairs, classrooms, and other supporting facilities, are also inadequate. The classrooms are starting to crumble, and the ceilings are eroding, posing a danger to students during the learning process. Furthermore, many of the chairs used by the students are damaged and unusable.

This demonstrates the public's understanding that many children in Indonesia still lack adequate learning facilities, and that local governments are neglecting the development of appropriate educational facilities, such as access to nets, proper chairs, and classrooms that do not endanger teachers or students during the learning process. Not only that, the Instagram account @seklah.tanahair also provides information or invitations to contribute directly, from opening donations to inviting the public to go directly to the locations that will be visited or schools that will be visited by the noisy district community.

The findings indicate that the @seklah.tanahair Instagram account functions as an effective information medium in disseminating the real conditions of education in remote areas of Indonesia. Through posts in the form of photos, short videos, and visual narratives, the Sekolah Tanah Air community highlights limited school infrastructure, inadequate learning facilities, and difficult access to education faced by teachers and students.

The uploaded content is not merely documentary but is accompanied by narratives that frame educational realities in emotional and informative ways. This aligns with New Media Theory (McQuail, 2011), which emphasizes that digital media enables message convergence, interactivity, and rapid, wide-reaching information distribution. Instagram allows the public not only to receive information but also to understand the social context underlying educational problems in remote areas.

[Figure Caption: viewers in instagram @seklah.tanahair]

Fig 6. Researcher

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These findings are reinforced by the high reach and view counts of several early posts, indicating that Instagram can serve as an alternative information source beyond mainstream media. On average, the posted content garnered approximately 2,000 to 1,000,000 views. Thus, Instagram @sekolah.tanahair plays a role as a public information medium that raises awareness of educational inequality in Indonesia.

2.) Instagram as a Space for Public Aspiration and Participation

Instagram is also a medium for public aspiration. Hashtags and comments on the account allow the public to voice their opinions, recommendations, and even criticisms of educational practices. Direct conversations with volunteers, educators, and other educational leaders in remote locations often take place using live streaming capabilities.

Participatory communication positions the audience as the subject of communication, not merely the object, claims Servaes (2002). Donations, reposting content, and actively participating in community-organized social events are examples of public participation in this context. Rather than simply receiving information, the public participates in the process of solving educational problems. Mikiewicz and de Araújo's (2021) concept of "digital solidarity," which states that social connectedness in cyberspace can be crucial social capital in fostering educational success, is supported by this phenomenon.

The concept of communication in introductory books on communication science, put forward by communication experts such as David K. Berlo, defines communication as having several elements: sender, message, medium, and receiver. Charles Osgood, Gerald Miller, and Melvin L. De Fluer further add several elements, including reciprocity, to illustrate successful communication. Therefore, it can be concluded that the important elements in communication are the sender/source, message, media, recipient, influence, and feedback (Hafied Cangara, 2016). In this study, the elements of communication that occurred through the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair can be described as follows:

a. Sender/source of message

In communication, the source or sender of a message, or communicator, is between people, whether from one person or more than one person in a group, such as an organization or institution (Hafied Cangara, 2016). In this study, the message sender is a group from the Noisy District community, namely the administrators of the social media account @sekolah.tanahair, which is part of the Noisy District community, conducting direct field observations of schools in remote areas of Indonesia. Before sending messages or information on the @sekolah.tanahair social media account, the Noisy District community documented the results of interviews, videos and photos in the field, and written captions to be shared on the @sekolah.tanahair Instagram account so that the wider public can understand and observe the conditions of schools in remote areas of Indonesia that have inadequate facilities in terms of road infrastructure, buildings, and other supporting facilities such as inadequate classrooms and other school equipment.

b. Message / information

A message is information conveyed by a sender to a recipient face-to-face or through communication media in the form of sound, writing, or symbols (Hafied Cangara, 2016). In this study, messages were conveyed through writing on images, captions, and the use of symbols in hashtags or tags in posts on the @sekolah.tanahair account. Researchers found messages contained in Instagram social media posts @sekolah.tanahair through videos, captions, and symbols contained in the posts. One of these was a post on July 28, 2025.

[Figure Caption: caption and narration Instagram @sekolah.tanahair]

Fig 7,8. Researcher

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The image above is one of the uploads from the Instagram account @sekolahtanahair in the upload there is a photo with a broken chair in the classroom and the additional text "Learning doesn't have to be luxurious, but it must be decent, there is no projector, no AC but they still learn" not only that the addition of a caption or description of the upload with the text "They don't need luxury, just need a decent space to dream, let's be part of their journey" and the use of several hashtags such as #indonesiapunyamimpi. The photo, the caption of the upload and the hashtags they use are the message they want to convey about the real state of education in remote areas of Indonesia through the images they share so that all children can get a decent education with the sentence "let's be part of their journey" namely the wider community and the government can participate in the development of decent education.

c. Media

Media is a tool used to transfer messages or information from the sender to the recipient or audience in interpersonal communication or mass communication (Hafied Cangara, 2016). In this study, it is included in open mass communication where everyone can see or listen through the media. The media used is Instagram as a message sending medium through uploads on the Instagram account @sekolahtanahair to send messages to the audience or the general public without any reach limitations and can interact directly through the comments column or special messages available in the Instagram application.

d. Recipient

The recipient is the target of the message sent by the source or sender. The recipient can be a single person or a group (Hafied Cangara, 2016). In this study, the recipients or intended audience are Instagram users, from the general public to government officials. This can be seen in several comments on the @sekolah.tanahair post.

e. Influence

Influence is the difference between what the recipient feels, thinks, and does before and after receiving a message that can be seen through attitudes or actions as a result of the recipient of the message (De Fleur, 1982). In a digital campaign carried out through the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair, the manager uses words or videos with narrative invitations that can influence, such as the use of the words "let's be part of their journey" or "let's donate" and also video and photo displays to influence and convince the audience to take actions in accordance with the manager's wishes, such as donating books and other materials.

f. Feedback

Feedback is a form of action from the recipient's influence or response after receiving a message (Hafied Cangara, 2016). In this study, feedback via the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair took the form of comments, sharing @sekolahtanahair's posts on the story feature on Instagram so that they can be seen by the wider community and participating in donations ranging from goods to money.

So, in addition to functioning as an information medium, Instagram @sekolah.tanahair also serves as a space for public aspiration and participation. Comment sections, direct messages, repost features, and hashtag usage enable audiences to express opinions, support, criticism, and recommendations related to educational issues.

The observed interactions demonstrate that audiences are not passive. The public actively engages by providing emotional responses, offering assistance, and recommending other schools in need of attention. This phenomenon reflects the concept of participatory communication proposed by Servaes (2002), in which communities are positioned as communication subjects rather than mere message recipients.

Public participation in the form of donations, volunteer involvement, and content sharing indicates the formation of digital solidarity. This aligns with the concept of "digital solidarity," which suggests that social connectedness in digital spaces can serve as social capital for driving tangible social change, particularly in education.

3.) Digital Campaign Strategy of the @sekolah.tanahair Instagram Account

According to Morissan, a digital campaign is a strategic communication effort using digital media to influence audience behavior, raise awareness, and change public opinion about an issue, product, or idea (Morissan, 2018). Meanwhile, a digital campaign strategy is an online-based communication planning process and uses various media, including websites, social media, and interactive content, to build connections with the public (Lattimore et al. 2017). So, a digital campaign strategy is a strategy carried out by utilizing digital or internet-based media such as applications, Instagram, TikTok, X, Facebook and others, with the aim of being more easily accessed by many people because there is no limit to the audience reach as long as there is internet. The selection of interesting media and messages and the active involvement of the audience so that communication goals can run optimally and successfully must have a good strategy.

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The digital campaign strategy implemented by the *Distrik Berisik* community through the @sekolah.tanahair account is systematically designed by leveraging Instagram's social media characteristics. The campaign aims to raise public awareness, build audience engagement, and encourage concrete actions.

Based on the digital campaign stages proposed by Smith and Lattimore et al., the strategy can be identified in three main stages. First, the awareness stage is achieved by presenting visual content depicting educational conditions in remote areas to build public awareness. Second, the engagement stage is realized through the use of interactive Instagram features such as comments, direct messages, and discussion invitations. Third, the action stage is reflected in calls for donations, volunteer participation, and campaign dissemination to broader audiences.

The selection of Instagram as a campaign medium is considered appropriate because the platform supports strong visual narratives and storytelling. Campaign messages are crafted persuasively, informatively, and emotionally through short captions, slogans, and consistent hashtags. This strategy strengthens campaign identity and helps audiences recognize and remember the conveyed messages.

The elements of a digital campaign strategy according to R.D Smith and Lattimore et.al are:

Determining communication objectives (awareness, engagement, action)

a.) Campaign objectives are the foundation of every digital campaign, emphasizing that objectives must be specific, realistic, structured, and time-bound (Smith.2017). In the digital context, there are three objectives, namely:

1.) Awareness

The goal of this stage is to present a program or issue to a wider audience. For example, the Noisy District community, on the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair, has been campaigning for education by sharing photos and videos of educational conditions in remote areas. The goal is to raise public and government awareness and contribute to improving the development of proper education.

2.) Engagement

In this stage, the sender attempts to engage with the audience through the features of the media used for the digital campaign. For example, the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair utilizes features like likes, comments, and messages to engage with the audience.

3.) Action

The third action aims to encourage the audience to take real actions such as donating, spreading the campaign more widely and participating in activities.

The three stages carried out by the Instagram account manager @sekolah.tanahair aim to increase public awareness of educational disparities, encourage community participation, and inspire the community to contribute directly in the form of material assistance such as volunteering or fundraising.

a.) Target audience analysis

According to Lattimore et al. (2017) Audience analysis is an important stage in understanding the target audience of a campaign, their information needs, and their digital activities and this strategy is called digital segmentation in digital campaigns. Segmentation is carried out based on psychographics (lifestyle, interests and values), online behavior (active time, digital media used, and level of interaction) and finally digital demographics (age, gender, occupation). This analysis can help to determine the right social media according to audience segmentation or characteristics.

In this study, Instagram was chosen as a social media for delivering messages in a digital campaign for educational development with an audience segmentation of approximately 18-30 years old with a basis of short video content and interesting photos as well as the use of appropriate captions and hashtags that are frequently searched by other users so that they are widely seen by the audience.

b.) Selection of digital media

According to Smith (2013), in selecting the right digital media as the primary communication medium in a digital campaign, several considerations are needed, namely, how the media can convey the message visually and interactively, the characteristics of the audience, and the type of message to be conveyed.

The choice of the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair as a communication medium for delivering a digital campaign on education development issues is highly appropriate. Instagram, because it can share not only text but also short videos and photos, further convincing the audience and greatly supports the smooth running of the digital campaign on education development in remote areas. Furthermore, Instagram currently has a large user base, approximately one billion users.

c.) Creating persuasive messages and visual narratives

A message is the information you want to convey to the public, or it can also be the core of a campaign. According to Lattimore et al. (2017), information or messages must be persuasive, informative, and inspiring. To capture the audience's attention, visual elements and storytelling are also needed in digital content creation to be more creative and attract a wider audience. Important elements in creating digital information include:

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- 1.) Clarity, that is, not being long-winded in its delivery, with writing or narration that is not hyperbolic or exaggerated, with the use of words that are easy for the audience to understand.
- 2.) Credibility, namely the information conveyed has a reliable source so as not to cause problems or losses to the related parties.
- 3.) Emotion (emotional appeal), namely the use of visual narratives or sentences that can create empathy and emotional closeness, such as the use of images or videos that show a very worrying situation.
- 4.) Visual consistency. This means using a logo, colors, and design style that are easily understood and recognized by the audience, as well as using a memorable slogan with unique characteristics.

In the digital campaign carried out on the Instagram account @sekolahtanahair, the narrative in the Instagram bio is "Guard the Homeland, Return to the Roots, I Love Indonesia" and the consistent use of hashtags in each upload such as #indonesiabalikbahagia, #sekolahtanahair and the logo of the school of homeland in every photo or video uploaded on its Instagram social media. d.) Evaluate digital campaign results

According to Smith (2013), measurements are conducted to determine the effectiveness of message use, audience reach, and the actual impact of changes in attitudes or actions within the audience, using available data.

Commonly used evaluation parameters are:

- 1.) Click-through rate (CTR), how many Instagram users click on the digital campaign link
- 2.) Engagement rate, which is the level of audience involvement or can also be called the recipient's response to messages such as likes, comments, shares, reposts.
- 3.) Reach (reach), the number of audiences who see digital campaign posts.
- 4.) Sentiment Analysis, looking at audience feedback that is positive, negative and neutral.
- 5.) Conversion rate, measuring the actions taken by the audience after viewing the uploaded digital campaign.

In the digital campaign research conducted on the @sekolah.tanahair Instagram account, the manager can conduct an evaluation using engagement rate, sentiment analysis, conversion rate, it can be concluded from the Instagram upload @sekolah.tanahair successfully in conveying the digital campaign for educational development in remote areas.

This success can be seen from the likes, comments, users who saw the first upload in March with 96 likes, 22 comments with narratives that are all positive, for example comments from the @m.fahanc account "bismillah many good prayers, may all these great things be made easy, aamiin ya rabb", from the account on behalf of @teman.mengajarofficial "really cool ka, hopefully we can collaborate yes", @truefadhil "let's continue that color for Indonesia" the responses in the comments column are all positive. On the upload on April 9, 92 likes, 14 comments and all positive, then the short video upload on May 20, 2025 has more than 100 likes, 38 positive comments such as the account under the name @ardann_13 "continue to be successful", @dronetipistipis "long live the homeland fighters" and viewed by 78.8 thousand Instagram users. On the upload on June 3, 2025 with 102 likes, 15 positive comments.

The data above shows that the evaluation results of the digital campaign for educational development on the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair were successful, with many positive comments, an increase in likes, and an increase in the number of people viewing the posts.

4.) Impact of the Digital Campaign on Educational Development

Interviews with beneficiaries indicate that Instagram marketing activities have had a significant impact. Several schools highlighted in the blog received increased public attention and donor support, leading to support in the form of books, educational resources, and even classroom construction.

There are social consequences beyond material ones, particularly increased awareness of the educational gap in Indonesia. This corroborates the findings of Wibowo, Gularso, and Purwaningsih (2024), who found that social solidarity is crucial for improving literacy standards and basic education. Instagram's function has evolved from mere entertainment to a vehicle for social change. In efforts to improve education in underdeveloped areas, this social media platform effectively enables two-way communication between the general public, communities, and the government.

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[Figure Caption: posting and documentation of donation submission]

Fig. 8.9,10 Researcher

From the image above, it proves the impact of the digital campaign carried out through Instagram @sekolah.tanahair for one of the schools in the South Sulawesi area, namely SDN 166 Barru, Pujananting, Barru Regency, South Sulawesi, there is donation assistance from the results of the open donation that was carried out, so that it can help to buy 50 new and decent chairs, 3 good whiteboards and repair the classroom so that students are more comfortable. So it can be seen the positive impact of the digital campaign for schools in remote areas of Indonesia.

The findings show that the digital campaign through Instagram @sekolah.tanahair has produced tangible impacts on educational development in the featured areas. Several highlighted schools received assistance in the form of desks, whiteboards, books, and classroom renovations as a result of fundraising and community support.

Beyond material impacts, the campaign also generated social impacts by increasing public awareness of educational inequality in Indonesia. Audiences became more sensitive to educational conditions in remote areas and were motivated to participate in improvement efforts. These findings are consistent with previous studies emphasizing the importance of social solidarity and community participation in enhancing educational quality.

Thus, Instagram has evolved beyond an entertainment medium into a tool for social change. The digital campaign conducted by the Sekolah Tanah Air community and *Distrik Berisik* community demonstrates that social media can serve as a two way communication bridge between society, social communities, and the government in promoting more equitable educational development.

Participation Audiens

The digital campaign carried out by the Sekolah Tanah Air community has generated a significant number of sympathizers from the public, particularly Instagram users who view the content shared through their official account, @sekolah.tanahair. This can be observed through the responses in the comment section, where users actively engage with the campaign on educational development. The content highlights real conditions of underprivileged schools, for example:

[Figure Caption: responses from followers and other users)

Fig. 11,12 Researcher

From the two images above, it can be seen that support from other Instagram users is reflected in the comments section, ranging from expressions of gratitude and words of encouragement to tangible forms of support such as material contributions and donations made by members of the public who are exposed to the digital campaign conducted by the Sekolah Tanah Air community

Synthesis of Findings and Theory

When linked to Lasswell's Model, the @sekolah.tanahair digital campaign fulfills all elements of communication. The *Distrik Berisik* community acts as the communicator (*who*), educational campaign messages are conveyed through visual narratives (*says what*), Instagram functions as the communication channel (*in which channel*), audiences include the public and government (*to whom*), and the resulting effects include increased awareness, engagement, and concrete actions (*with what effect*).

Overall, the findings affirm that utilizing Instagram as a medium for information, public aspiration, and digital campaigning can shape public opinion and foster participatory communication in the context of educational development in remote areas of Indonesia.

B. DISCUSSION

The study's conclusions show that Instagram serves as an interactive communication platform that promotes two-way interaction between content producers and viewers in addition to being a means of disseminating information. This is consistent with the features of McQuail's New Media Theory, especially with regard to user-generated content, interaction, and participation. Instagram facilitates multidirectional communication in which users actively participate in creating, reacting to, and amplifying messages, in contrast to traditional media, which often functions in a linear and one way fashion.

This dynamic is further reinforced by the strong audience participation in the comment area. Both emotional and cognitive involvement with the subject of educational disparity is reflected in audience responses, which include calls for social action, questions concerning contribution systems, and emotions of empathy. These exchanges show that communication on digital platforms encompasses more than just sending messages; it also involves individuals working together to create meaning.

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The interaction seen in the comment area exemplifies a dialogical communication process from the standpoint of Servaes' introduction of participatory communication. In addition to being passive recipients, audiences actively participate in shaping the conversation and broadening the campaign's appeal. A networked communication environment, where messages are naturally disseminated through peer-to-peer interaction, is also formed by people exchanging information in the comment area.

Examined through the prism of Maxwell McCombs and Donald Shaw's agenda setting theory, the public's attention has been successfully drawn to educational discrepancies by regular exposure to information. The level of audience participation, especially in the comment section, indicates that the problem has gone beyond simple awareness to a more profound degree of involvement and concern. In this regard, Instagram is crucial for promoting social concerns and influencing public opinion in addition to spreading information.

Additionally, the digital campaign's efficacy and legitimacy are enhanced by Yayasan Generasi Bisa's institutional involvement in partnership with the Distrik Berisik community. This collaboration between a grassroots community movement and a formal organizational structure shows that digital campaigns have greater impact when they are backed by both institutional legitimacy and community driven innovation. Aligning online communication with offline program execution guarantees that the campaign produces real social impacts rather than just being symbolic.

This study emphasizes the importance of grassroots digital activism in the education sector, in contrast to earlier research that mostly focused on digital campaigns in marketing or political contexts. According to the results, community based initiatives have clear benefits, especially when it comes to trust building, emotional resonance, and authenticity. This suggests that localized narratives and active involvement, as opposed to top down communication approaches, are increasingly influencing internet activism in Indonesia.

By expanding the use of new media and participatory communication theories within the framework of grassroots digital campaigns, this study theoretically advances communication studies. It illustrates how social media platforms, when bolstered by effective narrative techniques and engaged audience engagement, can serve as tools for social change.

In terms of methodology, this study demonstrates that a qualitative approach specifically, netnographic observation in conjunction with content analysis is successful in capturing the dynamics of digital communication. However, the results' limited generalizability due to the single case focus highlights the necessity for future studies to use comparative methods across various platforms or communities.

Practically speaking, the results show that communities, non governmental organizations, and legislators can strategically use Instagram as a tool for social mobilization and lobbying. Emotional tales, interactive engagement, and visual storytelling have all been shown to be successful in encouraging public participation and converting online contact into practical action.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study concludes that the Instagram account @sekolah.tanahair plays a significant and effective role as a digital campaign medium in highlighting educational inequality in remote areas of Indonesia. Through visual storytelling and interactive communication, the platform enables the rapid, wide, and engaging dissemination of information while simultaneously creating participatory spaces that encourage active public involvement. The campaign not only increases public awareness but also generates tangible outcomes, including moral support, donations, and direct community engagement in the field.

The findings demonstrate that Instagram functions beyond an informational platform, serving as a space for public aspiration and collective action. Audiences actively participate in the communication process by engaging with content, redistributing messages, and contributing to campaign goals. This indicates that digital campaigns are capable of transforming passive audiences into active participants, thereby strengthening participatory communication dynamics.

From a theoretical perspective, the study confirms that the digital campaign aligns with New Media Theory, where communication is interactive, networked, and participatory, allowing audiences to act as both consumers and producers of information. Furthermore, when examined through Lasswell's Model of Communication, the campaign fulfills all key elements: the Distrik Berisik community as the communicator, persuasive educational messages delivered through visual narratives, Instagram as the communication channel, the public and policymakers as target audiences, and the resulting effects in the form of increased awareness, engagement, and concrete social action.

The effectiveness of the campaign is also supported by its strategic communication approach, which includes clear objective setting, audience identification, appropriate media selection, persuasive message construction, and continuous evaluation of audience responses. These elements contribute to the success of the campaign in fostering public empathy and mobilizing collective participation. The tangible impact is reflected in increased attention to educational issues in remote areas, as well as the provision of educational support such as learning facilities and school improvements.

This study offers several important implications. For governments, social media can function as an alternative tool for participatory mapping and monitoring of educational issues in remote regions. For communities and non governmental organizations, Instagram proves to be an effective platform for advocacy, mobilization of support, and the strengthening of social solidarity. For digital

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campaign practitioners, the findings emphasize the importance of visual storytelling and two way interaction as key factors in achieving effective and impactful communication.

However, this study has limitations, particularly its focus on a single case study and one social media platform, which limits the generalizability of the findings. In addition, the measurement of campaign impact remains qualitative and has not been supported by in depth quantitative analysis.

Future research is therefore recommended to adopt comparative approaches across multiple digital platforms, involve broader stakeholders including audiences and policymakers, and integrate both qualitative and quantitative methods to provide a more comprehensive understanding of digital campaign impacts.

Overall, this study affirms that Instagram functions not only as an entertainment medium but also as a strategic tool for social transformation. With creative, structured, and well planned utilization, youth driven digital campaigns have the potential to move beyond online engagement and become tangible social movements that contribute to equitable education and sustainable development in Indonesia.

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